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IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR MANAGING FINANCIAL RESOURCES OF ENTERPRISES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract: This article is devoted to defining the features of the financial management system in the activities of modern enterprises in modern conditions. It shows the detailed goals and major areas of the enterprise financial management system, explores the problems of developing a financial management system in commercial enterprises, as well as solutions.

Keywords: financial management systems, financial management object, financial management subject, own funds, borrowed funds financial resources.

Introducing

Management of an enterprise's financial resources is a system that combines a variety of methods, operations, levers and techniques for influencing various types of finance in order to achieve a certain result. The enterprise's financial resource management system should include an analysis of factors for the effective use of financial resources in the short and long term, included in the financial policy, which is based on a specific area of activity of financial services. The importance of the functions of financial resource management subjects in the management system is highlighted by enterprise management tools and management subjects who are responsible for making management decisions. Increasing the efficiency of the management system depends on the degree to which financial managers realize their tasks, including providing the enterprise with financial resources and increasing the efficiency of their use .

A number of researchers in the field of financial management adhere to the point of view according to which the management of an enterprise's financial resources is a system, while another part of the authors considers this concept as a process through which the amount of capital of an enterprise is influenced. In our opinion, in the financial management system it is necessary to highlight a separate subsystem "management of enterprise financial resources", which will provide the enterprise with the necessary financial resources for its sustainable development. Management of financial resources as a system includes the principles and methods of developing and implementing management decisions related to ensuring their effective formation, distribution and use in the process of economic activity."

Having summarized the research of a number of academic economists, we can conclude that the management of an enterprise's financial resources is one of the most important. At the same time, taking into account the particular importance of the efficient use of financial resources by an enterprise, we propose to consider the functions of management subjects whose activities are aimed at achieving the tactical and strategic goals of the enterprise, since it is on these structural elements of the system, on the correctness of their adoption of management decisions, that the further development of the enterprise as a whole depends.

The responsibilities of the highest level of management of an enterprise's financial resources include strategic management, i.e., development and determination of priority directions for the development of the enterprise. These include ensuring consistently high rates of economic development of the enterprise, strengthening the competitive position in the market, reducing costs associated with production activities, and achieving high financial performance.

As can be seen from Figure 1, the responsibilities of the highest level of management of an enterprise's financial resources include strategic management, i.e., development and determination of priority directions for the development of the enterprise. These include ensuring consistently high rates of economic development of the enterprise, strengthening the competitive position in the market, reducing costs associated with production activities, and achieving high financial performance. The process of long-term (strategic) management of financial resources at an enterprise is impossible without a properly developed financial policy, which is formed at the highest level of management and represents a kind of regulatory framework regarding the management of monetary capital. The goal of financial policy is the phased implementation of the chosen strategy of the enterprise, for which the following tasks are solved: choosing the most effective ways to implement the strategy, ensuring the solvency and financial stability of the enterprise, achieving the optimal ratio of the organization's own and borrowed capital.

The strategy and tactics of an enterprise's financial policy are closely interrelated, and a correctly chosen strategy creates favorable opportunities for solving tactical problems. Planning, which covers the enterprise's current activities and lasts up to one year, is called operational planning.

The activities of the middle level of the organizational structure are associated with the medium-term management of the enterprise's financial resources, sources of financing and investment activities. Management of sources of financing is associated with the formation of internal and external, short-term and long-term sources of financial resources, analysis of the conditions for their attraction, and determination of

the cost of attracted capital. In addition, the functions of this level of management include assessing the feasibility of attracting borrowed funds and using own funds and forming the optimal capital structure of the enterprise.

The long-term (strategic) management of financial resources in an enterprise cannot be carried out without a properly developed financial policy, which is formed at the highest management level and represents a regulatory framework for managing monetary capital. The goal of financial policy is the phased implementation of the chosen strategy of the enterprise, for which the following tasks are solved: choosing the most effective ways to implement the strategy, ensuring the solvency and financial stability of the enterprise, achieving the optimal ratio of the organization's own and borrowed capital.

The strategy and tactics of an enterprise's financial policy are closely interrelated, and a correctly chosen strategy creates the necessary financial capabilities to solve tactical problems. Operational planning, covering the current activities of the enterprise with a perspective of up to one year, and medium-term management of financial resources, sources of financing and investment activities, represent the activities of the middle level of the organizational structure.

The science of enterprise financial management is characterized by reflecting the logic of making financial decisions, as well as a set of measures (recommendations) to improve planning and control over finances at the level of business entities.

The degree of development of the problem. Enterprise financial management as a promising direction in economic science combines theoretical developments in the field of financial management, as well as applied ones relating to financial levers and management methods.

Foreign economists about the financial management system should be noted: V.G. Belolipetsky, W. Sharp, G. Alexander, J. Bailey, V. A. Gerasimenko, Yu. Ya. Vavilova, L. I. Goncharenk, V. N. Vyatkin, I. A. Blank E. F. Sysoeva, A N. Gavrilova, I. Ya. Lukasevich, V. E. Leontiev, A. D. Sheremet, A. F. Ionova.

Among the domestic scientists who studied the priority issues of adapting the financial resource management system to market conditions directly or indirectly: B. Toshmurodova, N. Zhumaev, S. Elmirzaev, E. Hoshimov, Sh. Khazhibaev, N. Muminov, N. Tursunova, M. Khamidulin , V. Kotov, R. Karlibaeva, F. Khamidova, M. Pulatova and others.

Meanwhile, the studies conducted by the above scientists were mainly devoted to theoretical, methodological issues of the financial management system; they considered only some categories and areas of increasing the efficiency of financial resources. But real practical issues related to the process of improving the financial

management system in modern market conditions and the factors for their positive solution were not considered in their works.

The research methodology is based on general scientific methods: analysis and synthesis, systemic, logical and comparative analysis, sample surveys. Reference, statistical and regulatory materials on the problem under study were used.

Analysis and results. Organization of financial management of an enterprise is a set of measures aimed at timely and complete provision of the company with financial resources and their rational use. The main goal of the financial management system is to maximize the value of the enterprise by increasing capital.

The financial management system of an enterprise contributes to the achievement of tactical and strategic goals of a business entity and consists of two subsystems (Fig. 1.).

The object of financial management is a set of conditions for the circulation of funds and the movement of cash flows, the circulation of value, the movement of financial relations and financial resources arising in the external and internal environment of the organization.

The subject of financial management is financial instruments, technical means, methods, specialists that form a single financial structure for the rational functioning of the management object.

The specific goal of the financial management system is to ensure maximization of the welfare of the owners of the enterprise (partners and shareholders) in the current and future periods.

Ensuring the formation of the required amount of financial resources in accordance with the objectives of the enterprise's development in the future

Ensuring the most efficient use of the generated volume of financial resources in the main areas of the organization's activities

Optimization of cash flow

Ensuring profit maximization at the envisaged level of financial risk

Figure 1. The main tasks of the enterprise financial management system

It should be noted that the financial management system of enterprises has shown that it has several significant areas. (Fig.1.)

The biggest mistake of many domestic entrepreneurs is their underestimation of financial flow management. Some entrepreneurs explain this by the particular complexity of financial problems, and therefore delegate their powers to subordinates.

This position is erroneous: in no way can you direct or independently control incoming and outgoing cash flows. In the movement of these flows, the real result of entrepreneurial activity is concentrated and those opportunities for increasing business performance that the entrepreneur is looking for are hidden. Therefore, a domestic entrepreneur, first of all, needs to master all the basic principles and approaches of financial management and understand them well, otherwise he is doomed to failure.

Table 1

Number of operating enterprises and organizations by economic sectors

Sectors	2020	2021	2022	2023
Total	398133	475197	528929	592371
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	29379	41321	46501	53808
Industry	70576	83539	91152	98805
Construction	36199	40950	43695	46971
Trade	101081	132192	157129	182917
Transportation and storage	15360	17301	18251	20666
Accommodation and food services	25636	30111	33104	36811
Information and communication	7901	9517	10587	12204
Health and social service provision	7903	9145	10391	11597
Others	104098	111121	118119	128592

The total number of businesses in the country continues to grow between 2020 and 2023. During this period, the total number of enterprises increased by 194,238, representing an increase of 49%. The agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector also shows stable growth, increasing by 24,429 enterprises (an increase of 83%) during the

specified period. Industry: there is moderate growth in industry with an increase of 28,229 enterprises (an increase of 40%).

Figure 3. Major areas of enterprise financial management

Next, we will consider the financial condition of JSC Thermal Power Plants. JSC Thermal Power Plants is considered a major producer and supplier of electrical and thermal energy and ensures full satisfaction of the electrical energy needs of economic sectors and the population. Today, 85 percent of the electrical energy generated in Uzbekistan comes from Thermal Power Plants JSC.

Table 2

Final financial results of JSC Thermal Power Plants

Indicator name	2020 г.	2021 г.	2022 г.
Net revenue from sales of products (goods, works and services)		108 725 873	174 297 468
Cost price		102 995 841	168 213 941
Gross profit		5 730 032	6 083 527
Expenses of the period, total, including:	30 514 110	4 451 369	8 649 817
Administrative expenses	17 735 297	2 324 342	2 662 870
Other operating expenses	12 778 813	2 031 751	5 467 533

Other income from core activities	122 707 982	1 993 997	7 895 292
Profit (loss) from core activities	92 193 872	3 272 660	5 329 002
Income from financing activities	12 880 024		
Dividend income	10 784 873		100 822
Expenses related to financial activities, including	201 657	26 035	574 463
Losses from foreign exchange differences	86 073		
Profit (loss) from general economic activities	104 872 239	3 246 625	4 855 361
Profit (loss) before payment of income tax)	104 872 239	3 246 625	4 855 361
Income tax (profit)	15 040 837	580 204	1 204 769
Net profit (loss) of the reporting period	89 831 402	2 666 421	3 650 592

Based on the calculated data, I can say that in 2022, other income from core activities increased by 296% compared to 2021. Just like in 2021, the largest share in 2022 was net sales revenue, but compared to the previous reporting year during the period it increased by 60.3%. Also in 2021, compared to 2020, we see significant decreases in such sections as period expenses and administrative expenses, which led to an increase in net sales revenue. The smallest volume in 2022 was dividend income in the amount of 100,822, one hundred decreased by 2 times compared to 2020.

Table 3

Composition and structure of assets of JSC Thermal Power Plants

Indicator name	2020 г.	2021 г.	2022 г.
Fixed assets: at original cost	1 800 124	21 694 599	21 390 443
Wear amount	205 294	13 003 915	15 575 283
Residual (book) value	1 594 830	8 690 684	5 815 160
Long-term investments, everything. including:	13 270 981 389	3 330 907	3 310 917
Securities	13 182 653 165	234 365	234 365
Investments in dependent companies		3 096 542	3 076 552
Long-term accounts receivable	52 689 552	172 603	164 210
Inventories, total including	933 718	69 376 869	142 940 449

Productive reserves	933 718	66 639 960	133 168 006
Unfinished production		112 844	110 361
Finished products		2 586 751	9 648 268
Goods		37 314	13 814
Debtors	19 253 849	6 251 500	15 266 419
Debt of buyers and customers		38 720	266 810
Advances issued to personnel		3 280	
Advances issued to suppliers and contractors	484 191	1 839 748	1 542 472
Advance payments for taxes and fees to the budget	99 446	4 056 260	13 400 009
Advance payments to government trust funds and insurance		974	886
Other receivables	41 191	312 518	56 242
Cash, total, including:		481 658	309 036
Cash on settlement		65 817	307 368
Cash and equivalents	3 199 370	415 841	1 668
TOTAL for balance sheet assets	13 380 786 367	90 742 199	167 806 191

From the table we see that in 2022 commodity and material reserves increased by 106% compared to 2021 and amounted to 142,940,449 thousand soums. Advance payments to state trust funds decreased by 19% compared to 2021. Also in 2022, the debt of clients and customers increased by almost 600%. The total of all long-term assets in 2022 decreased by 23.8% compared to 2021 and by 99.9% compared to 2020. But despite this, balance sheet assets in 2022 increased by 84.9% compared to 2021, but compared to 2020 they decreased by 98.7%.

From the analysis it is clear that in 2020 the share of the enterprise's assets is Long-term investments with a volume of 99.614% of all assets and the smallest weight of 0.001% of all assets has advances to the budget. In 2021, a large volume of 76.455% was made up of inventories, and a small volume of 0.004% was made up of advances issued to employees. In 2022, the share, as in 2021, fell on inventories and amounted to 85.182% of all assets of the enterprise. Accounts receivable have not changed over the last 2 years, as well as advances directed to state trust funds. A smaller percentage of 0.001 was cash.

Table 4

Composition and structure of liabilities of JSC Thermal Power Plants

Indicator name	2020 г.	2021 г.	2022 г.
I. Sources of own funds			
Authorized capital	13 243 197 165	1 848 110	1 848 110
Added capital		219 585	219 585
Reserve capital	1 038 125	20 481 574	21 113 884
retained earnings	124 580 138	2 666 421	1 202 996
Target receipt	371 782	20 217 390	44 856 540
TOTAL FOR SECTION I	13 369 187 210	45 433 080	69 241 115
II. Liabilities			
Current liabilities, including:	11 599 157	45 309 119	98 565 076
current accounts payable	4 599 157	1 404 502	93 065 056
Debt to suppliers and contractors	184 485	746 026	884 177
Debt to subsidiaries and dependent companies	924 480	200 000	89 961 949
Advances received		43 307	3 854
Debt in payments to the budget	1 847 005	183 662	315 613
Arrears of payments to state trust funds	324 362	7 199	212 279
Debt to founders			1 105 573
Wage arrears	932 396		352 632
Short-term bank loans			20
Short-term loans	7 000 000	43 904 617	5 500 000
Other payables	386 429	224 308	228 979
TOTAL FOR SECTION II	11 599 157	45 309 119	98 565 076
TOTAL on balance sheet liabilities	13 380 786 367	90 742 199	167 806 191

The analysis shows that in 2020 the share of the company's liabilities was the authorized capital, its share was 98.972%, and the least weight was 0.001% debt to suppliers and contractors. In 2021, the liability share was 50.068% of current share liabilities and the net share was 0.008% of advances paid to government trust funds. In 2022, the share of current accounts payable was 55.46%, and short-term bank loans - 0.00001%.

Thus, drawing a conclusion from everything discussed above, we can say that in 2022 the Company increased the number of accounts payable instead of using short-term loans. The period of accounts payable has increased from 89 days in 2021 to 5,5803 days. In terms of inventory shelf life, Thermal Power Plants JSC did not effectively manage these assets, which resulted in the company's inability to generate a cash cycle and significant costs.

These expenses were due to the implementation of projects adopted between 2010 and 2022, in accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to achieve sustainability and preserve nature in the country.

Conclusion.

In general, having examined the scientific, theoretical and practical aspects of the research work, the following ways to improve the financial management system of enterprises to market conditions are recommended:

1. Improve methods of financial analysis and monitoring. This is manifested in assessing the economic situation of the enterprise, its solvency, stability, liquidity, and profitability.

The analysis is based on data from the balance sheet, profit and loss statements, and cash flows. Current indicators and information for previous periods are examined. Financial analysis allows you to draw conclusions about business prospects, plan the allocation of resources, and determine the need for financing - in short, make thoughtful and competent decisions.

2. Increase in equity capital. This strategy ensures increased financial stability due to the resulting increase in own working capital. Since own working capital represents the difference between own capital and fixed assets, a change in own capital will lead to a change in own working capital. Increasing equity capital is achieved by increasing the authorized capital, reducing dividends and increasing retained earnings and reserves, and increasing profitability.

3. Management of receivables and payables. An organization's solvency and financial health depend not only on the structure of the organization's obligations and the timing of their fulfillment but, first of all, on the availability and receipt of liquid assets, in which cash plays a significant role.

The level of solvency and financial stability of an organization depends on the turnover rate of accounts receivable, which characterizes the efficiency of the financial management system at enterprises.

4. Increasing the efficiency of financial control as the main tool of the financial management system. It is necessary to monitor the efficiency of business processes, budget execution, and compliance of actual indicators with planned ones. Financial

control helps optimize the use of financial resources and reduce costs. The reasons for unsuccessful financial control at national enterprises may include: low financial discipline, lack of accounting, and inaccurate data recorded in financial statements.

5. To improve the competence of the financial director, it is necessary to make high demands. A well-thought-out system for managing monetary resources helps to spend them with the greatest benefit for the development of the company and profit growth. The role of the CFO is multifaceted: every day he has to solve a wide variety of problems.

6. To create IT solutions for automating business processes that save time, ensure high accuracy of operations, simplify interaction with clients and partners and ultimately lead to increased profits, as well as ensure constant collection of information about the financial situation of business partners in order to reduce business risk. Today, all these goals are achieved with the help of a comprehensive solution - the introduction of software packages and applications for managing the financial resources of an enterprise.

The financial management system of an enterprise in modern conditions is the set of management tools that in modern conditions are necessary for every business entity that wants to increase competitiveness in the conditions of developing market relations.

A modern-minded financial director must predict the development trends of his industry and the problems that will arise in connection with this, and consistently build a pyramid of financial management of the enterprise that can solve them.

Thus, in summary, it can be noted that the pressing issues of financial management of commercial enterprises are the balance of economic, financial and social results of its work and the recommended ways to help resolve these issues.

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